

Data Collection Form

Name: Age:..... DM:.....

Date of Hospitalization: Duration:

Date of Consultation:

Initial Weight: Height:

Smoking: Yes NoPA Quit Yes No

Medical History:

- **Anxiety:** Yes No
Treatments: Start Date:
- **Hypertension (HTN):** Yes No
Treatments: Start Date:
- **Diabetes:** Yes No
Treatments: Start Date:
- **Dyslipidemia:** Yes No
Treatments: Start Date:
- **Other:**
.....
.....

Weight Loss: Yes No How many kilograms?

Severe Case in Family: Yes No

COVID-related Death in Family: Yes No

Symptoms	Initial	Persistent
Fatigue		
Fever		
Weightloss		
Weightloss (Kg)		
Chest pain		
Cough		
Palpitations		
Dyspnea	0 ☐ 1 ☐ 2 ☐ 3 ☐ 4 ☐	0 ☐ 1 ☐ 2 ☐ 3 ☐ 4 ☐
Nausea and vomiting		
Diarrhea		
Myalgia		
Arthralgia		
Headache		
Dizziness		
Cognitive impairment		
Dysgeusia		
Anosmia		